

4.1 Team cohesion

Creating team cohesion variables at Initial, Mid, Final

```
items <-  
list(items=c("INIT_I1T2.SQ001...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statem  
ents.about.your.team...Our.team.is.united.in.trying.to.reach.its.goals.for.performance.",  
  
"INIT_I1T2.SQ002...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statements.about.y  
our.team...We.all.take.responsibility.for.any.poor.performance.by.our.team.",  
"_  
INIT_I1T2.SQ003...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statements.about.yo  
ur.team...Our.team.members.have.conflicting.aspirations.for.the.team.s.performance."))  
results<-scoreItems(items, d, impute='none')  
d$INIT_task_cohesion <- as.numeric(results$scores)
```

```
items <-  
list(items=c("INIT_I1T2.SQ004...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statem  
ents.about.your.team...Members.of.this.team.stick.together.",  
"_  
INIT_I1T2.SQ005...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statements.about.yo  
ur.team...Members.of.our.team.would.rather.go.out.on.their.own.than.get.together.as.a.team.  
",  
  
"INIT_I1T2.SQ006...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statements.about.y  
our.team...Our.team.would.like.to.spend.time.together.outside.of.work."))  
results<-scoreItems(items, d, impute='none')  
d$INIT_social_cohesion <- as.numeric(results$scores)
```

```
items <-  
list(items=c("MID_MT3.SQ001...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statem  
ents.about.your.team...Our.team.is.united.in.trying.to.reach.its.goals.for.performance.",  
  
"MID_MT3.SQ002...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statements.about.y  
our.team...We.all.take.responsibility.for.any.poor.performance.by.our.team.",  
"_  
MID_MT3.SQ003...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statements.about.yo  
ur.team...Our.team.members.have.conflicting.aspirations.for.the.team.s.performance."))  
results<-scoreItems(items, d, impute='none')  
d$MID_task_cohesion <- as.numeric(results$scores)
```

```
items <-  
list(items=c("MID_MT3.SQ004...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statem  
ents.about.your.team...Members.of.this.team.stick.together.",
```

```

"
MID_MT3.SQ005...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statements.about.yo
ur.team...Members.of.our.team.would.rather.go.out.on.their.own.than.get.together.as.a.team.
",

"MID_MT3.SQ006...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statements.about.y
our.team...Our.team.would.like.to.spend.time.together.outside.of.work.")
results<-scoreItems(items, d, impute='none')
d$MID_social_cohesion <- as.numeric(results$scores)

items <-
list(items=c("FINAL_MT3.SQ001...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.sta
tements.about.your.team...Our.team.is.united.in.trying.to.reach.its.goals.for.performance.",

"FINAL_MT3.SQ002...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statements.about.
your.team...We.all.take.responsibility.for.any.poor.performance.by.our.team.",
"
FINAL_MT3.SQ003...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statements.about.
your.team...Our.team.members.have.conflicting.aspirations.for.the.team.s.performance."))
results<-scoreItems(items, d, impute='none')
d$FINAL_task_cohesion <- as.numeric(results$scores)

items <-
list(items=c("FINAL_MT3.SQ004...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.sta
tements.about.your.team...Members.of.this.team.stick.together.",
"
FINAL_MT3.SQ005...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statements.about.
your.team...Members.of.our.team.would.rather.go.out.on.their.own.than.get.together.as.a.tea
m.",

"FINAL_MT3.SQ006...How.much.do.you.agree.or.disagree.with.the.following.statements.about.
your.team...Our.team.would.like.to.spend.time.together.outside.of.work."))
results<-scoreItems(items, d, impute='none')
d$FINAL_social_cohesion <- as.numeric(results$scores)

# Comparing initial to final levels of task and social cohesion

t.test(d$INIT_task_cohesion, d$FINAL_task_cohesion, paired=T)
t.test(d$INIT_social_cohesion, d$FINAL_social_cohesion, paired=T)

# Weekly task cohesion – creating scales

items <- list(items=c("qw_16a_united",
"qw_16b_responsibility",

```

```

      "-qw_16c_aspirations"))
results<-scoreItems(items, x, impute='none')
results
x$team_cohesion <- as.numeric(results$scores)

# Mixed model analyses for weekly task cohesion

r1 <- lmer(team_cohesion ~ is_phase_two + (1|user_id), x); summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two', mod = r1) # to get pre- and post- means for this analysis

#### Comparing control and treatment group

# Creating variable to label 8 participants who had not received nudge

d$Condition <- 'Received nudge'
d$Condition[d$userID == '1794'] <- 'Not yet received nudge'
d$Condition[d$userID == '3237'] <- 'Not yet received nudge'
d$Condition[d$userID == '3766'] <- 'Not yet received nudge'
d$Condition[d$userID == '5236'] <- 'Not yet received nudge'
d$Condition[d$userID == '6545'] <- 'Not yet received nudge'
d$Condition[d$userID == '7538'] <- 'Not yet received nudge'
d$Condition[d$userID == '8142'] <- 'Not yet received nudge'
d$Condition[d$userID == '9115'] <- 'Not yet received nudge'
d$Condition <- as.factor(d$Condition)

table(d$Condition[d$MID_task_cohesion > 0]) # Number of participants per group

# Main analysis comparing cohesion for treatment and control groups

r1 <- lm(MID_task_cohesion ~ Condition, d); summary(r1)

mean(d$MID_task_cohesion[d$Condition == 'Received nudge'], na.rm = T);
sd(d$MID_task_cohesion[d$Condition == 'Received nudge'], na.rm = T)
mean(d$MID_task_cohesion[d$Condition == 'Not yet received nudge'], na.rm = T);
sd(d$MID_task_cohesion[d$Condition == 'Not yet received nudge'], na.rm = T)

r1 <- lm(MID_task_cohesion ~ Condition * INIT_task_cohesion, d); summary(r1)
effect('Condition * INIT_task_cohesion', mod=r1)

r1 <- lm(MID_social_cohesion ~ Condition, d); summary(r1)
mean(d$MID_social_cohesion[d$Condition == 'Received nudge'], na.rm = T);
sd(d$MID_social_cohesion[d$Condition == 'Received nudge'], na.rm = T)
mean(d$MID_social_cohesion[d$Condition == 'Not yet received nudge'], na.rm = T);
sd(d$MID_social_cohesion[d$Condition == 'Not yet received nudge'], na.rm = T)

```

```
r1 <- lm(MID_social_cohesion ~ Condition * INIT_social_cohesion, d); summary(r1)
effect('Condition * INIT_social_cohesion', mod=r1)
```

4.2 Productivity perceptions

Daily surveys

```
r1 <- lmer(qd_01_overallProductivityToday ~ is_phase_two + (1|user_id), x); summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two', mod = r1)
```

```
r1 <- lmer(qd_06_helpingAffectedProductivity ~ is_phase_two + (1|user_id), x); summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two', mod = r1)
```

```
r1 <- lmer(qd_01_overallProductivityToday ~ is_phase_two * INIT_task_cohesion +
(1|user_id), x); summary(r1) # moderation by initial task cohesion
effect('is_phase_two * INIT_task_cohesion', mod = r1)
```

```
r1 <- lmer(qd_01_overallProductivityToday ~ is_phase_two * INIT_social_cohesion +
(1|user_id), x); summary(r1) # moderation by initial social cohesion
effect('is_phase_two * INIT_social_cohesion', mod = r1)
```

Hourly surveys

```
r1 <- lmer(qh_01_productivity ~ is_phase_two + (1|user_id) + (1|date_day), x); summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two', mod = r1)
```

```
r1 <- lmer(qh_01_productivity ~ is_phase_two * INIT_task_cohesion + (1|user_id) +
(1|date_day), x); summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two * INIT_task_cohesion', mod = r1)
```

```
r1 <- lmer(qh_01_productivity ~ is_phase_two * INIT_social_cohesion + (1|user_id) +
(1|date_day), x); summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two * INIT_social_cohesion', mod = r1)
```

4.3 Well-being

Time well spent

```
r1 <- lmer(qh_04_timeWellSpent ~ is_phase_two + (1|user_id) + (1|date_day), x); summary(r1)
# daily
effect('is_phase_two, mod = r1)
```

```
r1 <- lmer(qd_08_timeWellSpent ~ is_phase_two + (1|user_id), x); summary(r1) # hourly
effect('is_phase_two', mod = r1)
```

Burnout

items <-

```
list(items=c("MID_I1B1.SQ001...How.often.does.each.of.the.following.statements.apply.to.you.
at.work...I.feel.burned.out.from.my.work.",
```

```
"MID_I1B1.SQ002...How.often.does.each.of.the.following.statements.apply.to.you.at.work...I.f
eel.fatigued.when.I.get.up.in.the.morning.and.have.to.face.another.day.on.the.job.",
```

```
"MID_I1B1.SQ003...How.often.does.each.of.the.following.statements.apply.to.you.at.work...I.f
eel.frustrated.by.my.job.",
```

```
"MID_I1B1.SQ004...How.often.does.each.of.the.following.statements.apply.to.you.at.work...I.f
eel.like.I.m.at.the.end.of.my.ropes."))
```

results

```
d$MID_burnout <- as.numeric(results$scores)
```

```
r1 <- lm(MID_burnout ~ Condition, d); summary(r1)
```

```
mean(d$MID_burnout[d$Condition == 'Received nudge'], na.rm = T); sd(d$MID_burnout
[d$Condition == 'Received nudge'], na.rm = T)
```

```
mean(d$MID_burnout [d$Condition == 'Not yet received nudge'], na.rm = T); sd(d$
MID_burnout[d$Condition == 'Not yet received nudge'], na.rm = T)
```

4.4 Work patterns

Daily surveys

```
r1 <- lmer(qd_02_timeSpentOwnTasks ~ is_phase_two + (1|user_id), x); summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two', mod = r1)
```

```
r1 <- lmer(qd_02_timeSpentOwnTasks ~ is_phase_two * INIT_task_cohesion + (1|user_id), x);
summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two * INIT_task_cohesion', mod = r1)
```

```
r1 <- lmer(qd_02_timeSpentOwnTasks ~ is_phase_two * INIT_social_cohesion + (1|user_id), x);
summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two * INIT_social_cohesion', mod = r1)
```

```
r1 <- lmer(qd_03_timeSpentHelping ~ is_phase_two + (1|user_id), x); summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two', mod = r1)
```

```
r1 <- lmer(qd_04_workTowardsOrganizationalGoals ~ is_phase_two + (1|user_id), x);
summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two', mod = r1)
```

Hourly surveys

```
r1 <- lmer(qh_02_ownTasks ~ is_phase_two + (1|user_id) + (1|date_day), x); summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two', mod = r1)
```

```
r1 <- lmer(qh_03_helpedTeam ~ is_phase_two + (1|user_id) + (1|date_day), x); summary(r1)
effect('is_phase_two', mod = r1)
```